

A FUTILE SEARCH FOR EDUCATIONAL HEROES AMIDST INDUSTRIAL STRIKES: TWENTY FIVE YEARS OF SAM UKALA’S ‘THE LAST HEROES’

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Abstract

One of the most debilitating factors that has plagued Nigerian education system has been the incessant industrial actions that have punctuated the flow of academic calendar in the country. The odious canker-worm has had several terrible effects on all the education stakeholders and the society at large. ‘The last Heroes’ by Professor Sam Ukala is a dark statement of the sorry state of education in Nigeria (here epitomized by ISMA) and the traumas of a heroic struggle to reinstate the future of posterity in the midst of faded and seemingly unrealisable dreams.

The writers of this paper are gravely concern about the conditions in the Nigeria education system especially at the tertiary level. Worried and scared stiff that even twenty five years premiered after the play was premiered, the situation remains unchanged. The protracted 8 month long Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) strike in 2022., several in the series forms the backdrop of their analyses of The Last Heroes. A call for a review of the causes of strikes in the education sector is an urgent demand.

Keyword: Strikes, Tertiary Education, brain-drain and posterity.

Introduction

The Longman Dictionary of contemporary English defines strike as a deliberate stoppage of work for a time because of a disagreement about pay, working conditions, etc. The term, also called labour strike, comes about when workers respond to grievances like dissatisfaction with government or company policy, salary and incentive problems, wrongful discharge or dismissal of employee, etc. A lot has been said about strikes in Nigeria, some have decried the action and its negative consequences, while some, especially in government quarters see it as mindless and completely illegal. However, strikes do have some positive impact as well. The nauseating thing about industrial action is sometimes the muzzling of legal officers at the industrial courts and the often obnoxious government policy of “No work, no pay”. Consequently, government workers/employees are cowed or browbeaten to submission with their tails between the legs, dreams or reason for the strike unfulfilled.

Are strikes legal?

Azubuikwe (2019) argues that the right of employees to strike determines not just when prospects for enjoying improvements in working and living conditions, but it is also a precondition for the sustenance of a just and democratic society. This right is however restricted by labour laws and practically suppressed in the course of actual actions in Nigeria. Strikes act as a means of the trade unions acting as a counter power to checkmate the excesses state often display in the act of dispensing their constitutional duties.

Therefore, strikes or industrial actions called or embarked upon by workers' when done must be under the ambits of the principles established by the International Labour Organization (ILO). Azubuikwe (2016) traces this line of argument further when he claims, that whether in the public or private sector, strikes are a fundamental measure of the democratic values of a society. The United Nations, European Union, African Union, etc recognizes industrial actions as a keystone of modern industrial society. Macfarlane (1981), Abugu (2015) agree that any society which seeks to become democratic must secure that right.

Workers, worldwide, have similar characteristics. They are, for example, desirous of recognition, fair wages and emoluments/incentives, job security and better working conditions. Most often than not the employer cannot satisfy all these needs. Such frictions/disagreement gives rise to disputes and strikes (Okene, 2007).

History of strikes in Nigeria: Special Focus on Tertiary Institutions

The first industrial action by University lecturers in Nigeria was recorded in the 1973/74 session where the Union formerly under the aegis of Nigerian Association of University Teachers (NAUT) was barely four years old. Following the 1988 national strike, called to ask for better welfare package for university lecturers and to seek university autonomy, the union earned itself a proscription on the 7th of August that year. It was de-proscribed in 1990 only to be banned later on August 23rd 1992. The ban was lifted on 3rd September, 1992.

The chronology of industrial action in these institutions shows a very high frequency rate and most of them for the same reasons; a clear indication of the adamant and undemocratic nature of our national political leadership.

A close study of the frequency of these strikes since the beginning of the Fourth Republic in 1999, reveals that ASUU has engaged in the exercise about 17 times:

Year		Period
1999	-	5 months
2001	-	3 months
2002	-	2 weeks
2003	-	6 months
2005	-	2 weeks
2006	-	3 days
2007	-	3 months
2008	-	1 week
2009	-	4 months
2010	-	5 months
2011	-	59 days
2013	-	5 months
2017	-	1 month
2018	-	3 months
2020	-	9 months

2022 - 8 months.

A cumulative statistic of the period ASUU has embarked on strike in the current democratic dispensation adds up to more than five years. It is equally noticed that these strike actions occurred always every year. No one is certain if 2023 will be spared students' frustration and parents agony as we wait anxiously for an academic eldorado. The strikes are causing a monumental damage to our collective sensibilities. The exercise has obviously done more harm than good to the entire system and scheme of things. This leads to the questions: who are the culprits and what is the way forward? Government has been blamed for their insincerity in attending to the problems of tertiary institutions while ASUU has also received knocks for their impatience at the negotiating table. The cankerworm has gone viral, as almost all segments of the tertiary education sector has begun to adopt the method as the best option to settling scores with the government: FG or state government.

Effects of Strikes on Stake Holders of the Education Sector

The question: "Are there any effects on the stakeholder of the education sector?" is at most a rhetorical one. The government, lecturers/other tertiary institution workers, students of the institutions and their parents have one negative effect or the other each time a strike is embarked upon.

Embarking on strike makes students to spend more than the statutory duration in school. The implication is that such students may not meet up with the age requirement for entry-level jobs and National Youth Service Corps scheme. Students and lecturers may suffer emotional and psychological maladjustment. There is also the dreaded rise in youthful crime and immorality levels. Kidnapping for ransom, armed robbery, fraud (yahoo), rape, etc are the obvious consequences.

Parents are most hard-hit by the exercise as they pay the bills for their wards. They expect that at a particular point in time, they would be relieved from paying rents (pay-rents for parents) and can thus enjoy the fruits of their labour. All these hopes are often dashed by incessant strikes in the education sector.

The government is often seen as being insensitive to the society's plight whereas the overloaded and over bloated central government is grappling with myriad of problems like security, health care, the economy itself, etc. Thus, ASUU strike may be the least of her challenges; more-so when millions of graduates remain unemployed. The researchers' guess is as good as anyone else's on the issue at state.

If there are any positives resulting from strikes, it might be that they are an opportunity to help articulate challenges in any sector on strike for government's attention. The society at large might also begin to truly see why tertiary institutions are 'complaining' always.

Sam Ukala's 'The Last Heroes'

A Dramatic Twist to ASUU/ASUP Strikes

Prior to the commencement of the civilian administration in Nigeria in 1999, Prof. Sam Ukala had in 1997 penned the drama; 'The Last Heroes'. It was, as pointed out earlier, a bold attempt from the academia to stand up to the military jackboot (Junta) at the time. The heroic struggle at the imaginary University of Isma, formed the background of the play.

Emeritus Professor Samuel Chinedum Ukala who passed away in September, 2001 at the age of 73 made his mark in the academic as a playwright. He was a teacher, theorist, theatre director and an actor. He had several collection of plays to his credit including Akpakaland and Iredi War,

which won the prestigious LNG prize for the literature in 2014. He also wrote fiction and poetry and got the Association of Nigeria Authors (ANA) prize.

The Mbiri – born literary theorist propounded the theory of folkism to capture the trappings of the dramatic apprehension of post colonial experience in the play under review, the dramatist creates a dramatic impression of the philosophy of existentialism. This 20th century philosophical movement emphasizes the uniqueness of each human existence in freely making its self-defining choices. Through the classroom interaction, Prof. Bayo Ibitayo one of Ukala’s character’s has been able to educate his students to reason along the existential philosophical line as we hear one of them (Nnamdi) say:

“Philosophy of despair and isolation.
No hope in god and in religion.
No hope in science
No hope in traditional values
Man is isolated even in a crowd
and must fend for himself as an individual.
At birth, man is a tabula rasa and his existence
precedes his essence.
His world is materialistic and death is the ultimate.
Therefore, if man must live an authentic life, he
must make choices that would bring meaning to
his individual life, regardless of convention and dogmas.
But he must take responsibility for those choices”.

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This huge statement from the character no doubt carries a heavy authorial weight. The philosophy is corroborated by Prof. Who opines quite early in the play that there is the need for knowledge to topple ignorance which was currently on the throne of our land. The universities in the nation of Isma are supposed to be on strike but some lecturers like Prof are not obeying the strike order, claiming that at his level as a university Professor, he is not supposed to be on strike. This action will no doubt attract ‘picketing’ from the union of protesting/striking lecturers. However, as the play develops, we notice that Prof. is actually citing students to violence with his ideological lectures.

Students are usually the worst affected by strikes as Ike another student opines: “Strike, strike, strike everyday! You enrol in a university and never know when you’d graduate’. I am sick and tired of it all’.

They are obviously frustrated and in an understanding statement Nnamdi explains that while bearing an escaping Prof. Bayo through a window earlier on, the latter was ‘a mere egg shell’. He reasons that hunger was the cause of the strike, since lecturers do not eat well.

The fast-moving one act drama shifts attention to a scene showing the discussion between Dr. Danbaba – the Deputy Vice-Chancellor (DVC) with the VC. The former is pro-government, the eye of the minister of education and considers’ the likes of Professor Ibitayo as being unpatriotic; his likes, he opines have been cleared off like puss from a boil; He pretends to be unaware of the dearth of academics in the country. He even goes ahead to suggest that a video recording of the anti-strike lecturers and lecturers attendance Register be sent to the military junta as evidence that university of Isma was calm. This is definitely an arm twisting device often embarked upon by Nigerian government officials to ensure there is division in the camp of the striking lecturers’.

The military option suggested by the DVC to have armed police and army surround lecture halls is condemned by the Students Union. Nnamdi says the students do not need armed wardens on guard, while they learn. The army and police have never been their friends and now they desire to kill their hungry lecturers. Do guns move on the blackboard or publish in journals? He queries.

The confrontation that ensues lead to the death, injury and rape of some students by the armed military men. The soldiers true intention was mistaken for antagonism with the students.

Danbaba came to the position of DVC by nepotism and tribalism and his crazy desire was to discredit his boss and displace him. Meanwhile, the play shifts to Prof's house where some students: Amina and Bola have taken refuge away from the pandemonium on campus. The V.C has also run to hide in the Prof's lodge, being on the run from Danbaba's frame-up. The evidence of the killers' (military) havoc captured by Nnamdi's Camera is destroyed by the mad dogs (military men). Ukala spares no harsh adjective to describe the despotic and despicable acts of the military.

The situation in running a university in Nigeria is aptly captured by V.C when he says "Running a university here is like splitting a hair with an axe. It is like sharing an ant among a million people". (p. 97-98)

Uneasy calm is restored to the university campus after Alli who feigns the special Adviser to Minister, orders the commissioner of police to withdraw the military presence off campus. The reality is that with three students killed, five injured, several looted bodies raped to tatters and others languishing in pains there cannot be any harmonious calm, but an uneasy pseudo-calm.

Majority of Nigerian academics at the time live on the reminisces of the glorious past as there are no lasting relics carried over to the present or any sweet memorabilia to be preserved for the unborn tomorrow. Prof. in a brief reverie rhapsodizes about the experiences he had with Prof Obiora, the VC back at Rockland, New York, USA. Such sweet moments shared with relish, keeps these disenchanting lecturers occasionally aglow in spite of the rot-in the system. Lecturers like Prof. Lindfors are resigning and drifting abroad, leaving an apparent brain drain ripple effect. Prof. Bayo says:

"My country universities are losing teachers in droves to universities all over the world. The future of our nation is crumbling like a sand dome while we sweat out our blood building other nations". (p. 101).

The simple truth is captured in the last clause "... building other nations". Nigerian experts in all fields of life are noticed everywhere in the advanced countries. Breaking records and setting the pace for others to follow. The bread-and-butter-question is why can Nigeria not set up the enabling situation and environment for these academics and industrial cum techno gurus to flourish?

The challenge of nation building and patriotism is a heavy burden on the heart of Prof. Bayo and his wife hence their decision to remain at Isma to demonstrate the commitment rather than run away. As for back as 1997, the call for a research into the causes of the collapse of our educational system has been a clarion call by educationists like Ukala. We hear him speak through Prof. Bayo: "A thorough research needs to be done to determine the collapse of our educational system and the possible remedies"... He wants to be counted among such researchers. This cannot be possible in a country that has lost value for education.

In fact, three factors determine the success of this fact as Ada reasons on Nigeria soil: connection to top brass of military, political status and wealth. It is not enough to be a Professor.

Who can make noise and not be heard. Hunger and poverty does not respect book knowledge in Nigeria. Illiterate power barons made final decisions then and even now. Prof. is undaunted and he resists Bimpe and Nwafor (his kid's) plea for him to join them to escape to USA, and seek assylum on the grounds of the negativities of racism and slavery.

All the negative government activities like school closure, students being ordered to vacate hostels, striking lecturers to vacate lodging quarters etc are fully applied here. The dialogue advocated by Prof. and V.C is jettisoned in favour of a draconian, slave driver government option. All these are designed to force the unfriendly educational policies down the people's (educational implementor/lecturers) throats.

The eventual result of Danbaba's plot is the displacement of Prof. Obiora. The former is made the acting V.C of Isma University and he unleashes a new madness and raw bestiality on the lecturers for daring to ask government for better job conditions. The lecturers' love for sound education as since-qua-non to safeguarding their children's future is being met with brute force and abnoxious anti-people government policies. The students' body now know better; that there is 'a beast' called government which does not buy into the idea of the pen being mightier than the sword. To send home their point, they arrange a mock funeral to mark the death of the 'biro' which effigy is borne as the symbolic corpse. Nnamdi's speech on page 113 points to the last Heroes unfortunate fate:

... we speak no ill of you,
we call you our fallen hero even
though you were never a hero
in our land. You never bloomed
for you were the seed that fell
in a thicket of thorns. Tending you
was wasteful of young ambition,
wasteful of old commitment...
Your last heroes have passed by in
coffins of mangled dreams...
Isma's sacrifice of tomorrow's productivity
and our own offering of disgust"... (p. 113)

This is the students' conclusion about the sorry state of education in Nigeria.

It is extremely difficult for any academic not be emotionally involved in the plight of tertiary institution staff in Nigeria. The blatant disregard for education when balanced against other sectors like security, politics, health and oil is grossly unacceptable. Painful as the effects of strikes may be, they will continue to recur/reoccur so long as those concerned refuse to do the needful.

Ukala was definitely towing the line of the protest spirit of the day. For Osofisan Had opined that:

"As writers, we accepted that our predecessors had invented
a tool for us but that our own vocation would be to seize this
tool, and direct it to the work of social, political, economic
and cultural liberation" ... (p. 45-46)

The implication of this fastening spirit of protest is what Agho (2011) captures when he ponders that "writers use their creative works to attack the inanities of those in the corridors of power, the abuse of political office and the problem of bad leadership ..." (p. 15)

The second part of the play begins with the fact that lecturers have been reduced to beggars by hunger occasioned by unpaid wages. The people have to learn the ‘Babi Allah’ (give to God) song as Osawu points out. Adesua describes the hunger in hyperbolic realism thus: “...Can’t you hear hunger bellowing in my belly? Don’t you hear granite grating away my bum and knuckles as I crawl...” (p. 110)

The symbolism of Nigeria’s unfortunate situation is ridiculously told in satirisms of the falling and rising cripple who has nothing to stand on but her bottom. Indeed the whole system is smeared up by our poo (mess).

The end of educational rascality and government’s irresponsibility is very near. Danbaba’s lavish lifestyle becomes his undoing as Prof. Bayo and Amina connive to collect a dossier of his financial recklessness unknown to him. Indeed Danbaba’s patriotism is nothing but putrid falsehood and mindless opportunism.

The attitude of the youths to education today is summarized in the slogan/historical question: “who school help”?

Danbaba now posing as Alhaji drops this hint when he says: “many students now abandon the university in pursuit of money” (p. 130). Yahoo is the order of the day. Ukala prophetically foresaw all these years ago.

Most of the lecturers have got into other vocations like the police, brewery workers, fast-food/joint operators, etc. Money and the quest for power, opines the playwright is the prime motif for these vocational switch. The nation is described in countless negatives: degraded, despoiled, dilapidated, deconstructed, defoliated, derogated, deracinated, desighted, demobilized, deranged, despised, demolished, ... she is like a woman deflowered and abandoned.

The play closes on the victorious note of Danababa (Alhaji) finally caught in the macabre web of his lustful and rapaciously corrupt lifestyle. Danbaba obviously symbolizes government who has all these while been able to crush all oppositions. Prof. and Amina have put a seal on his doom and as he gets beaten, there is hope that he will be tried in a true court and jailed. The people’s victory will most certainly put an end to all managements. (govt.) shenanigans – when ‘the dead mourn the living’. As police woman submits “it’s about the dead rising to question their killers, the trial of the living by the dead” (p. 144).

Conclusion

Osuntokun (2022) assents that our country is not mobilized for production and productivity. Nigerian’s reliance on collection of commission on oil and gas exports coupled with the fact that taxes are paid only by the salaries workers gives government the leverage to ignore the complaints of the masses. It thus has the free hand to determine arbitrarily which sector of the economy to favour and which to overlook. Little wonder why education in Nigeria is not considered as a critical sector when compared to security. The fact that incessant strikes will lower the standard and rating of Nigerian educational institutions is trite. Government needs to honour agreements and stop renegeing on such to guarantee truce. Dialogue and constant negotiation is needed not a blatant refusal to shift ground.

The students and parents are always at the unpleasant end of the debate while the society is burdened with the dilemma of how to cope with the vices unleashed on it by the students who are not in school as a result strikes. The way out of this social-cum educational quagmire this becomes a most welcome development.

The ripple-effect of ASSUU strikes is being noticed in the ascendancy of the action in sister unions like ASUP (Academic Staff Union of Polytechnic) and allied institutions.

Recommendation

Nigerian tertiary institutions should legally agitate for autonomy. This will help each government institution cost education of a student appropriately and thus give parents the choice on where to educate their wards. Poor parents can apply for scholarships.

Adequate government funding of these institutions must be guaranteed. These funding along with the schools internally generated revenue (IGR) should go a long way in catering for schools needs.

In an addition to the systematic takeover of schools from the vice like grip of governments control, credible academics and resource manager should be put in charge of the school's finances to ensure proper utilization of these funds.

Sponsorship of projects and other aids can be provided by world development banks, private industries, international bodies like IMF and NGO's.

It is also important that negotiations and arbitrations in times of crises should be fair, open-ended and frank. Rigidity and destructive/vindictive ideologies should be left outside the negotiating table.

Bodies like Education Tax Fund, and Tertiary Education Trust Fund should redouble effort in more sponsorship of education issues in the country-to meet physical and manpower needs of these institutions.

Generally, education should be given its pride of place in the scheme of things in Nigeria. A state of emergency should be declared in the sector because education is critical to national survival.

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